

Tsallis Entropy and e_i/T power $-1/g$ Solution Instead of $\exp q$

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In (1), the authors start with an a priori normalized power law probability $p(e) = C (e/T)^{-g}$ and proceed to show that it leads to a Tsallis type entropy, by using the definition: $S = k \sum_i g(p(e_i))$ with $g(p_i) = 0$ if $p_i = 0$ or $p_i = 1$ and $0 = \sum_i (e_i - kT dg(p_i)/dp_i) dp_i$ defined = $\sum_i K_i dp_i$. In other words, the authors of (1) set $dg(p_i)/dp_i = 1/(kT) \{e_i - K_i\}$ and integrate to find an entropy and show it is in the form of Tsallis entropy: $1/(1-q)$ constant $\{1 - \sum_i p_i^q\}$. Thus, they argue that a pure power law probability, and not just $\exp q(e_i/T)$, is associated with Tsallis entropy. The author's use the average value of e_i as being formed by $\sum_i e_i p(e_i)$ and only focus on normalized $p(e_i)$.

In previous notes (2), we have argued that Shannon's entropy and regular Tsallis entropy follow from a function $F(p(e_i))$ defined such that: $F(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$ together with: $p(e_i) dF/dp = 1$ and $p(e_i)^q dF/dp = 1$ in the Shannon and Tsallis cases respectively. Here $p(e_i)$ is unnormalized.

We argued in these notes that $F(p)$ contains all of the e_i information, and so writing $p(e_i) F(e_i)$ and taking $d/dp(e_i)$ means that the term $F(e_i)$ displays all of the e_i/T information and so $p(e_i) dF/dp(e_i)$ need not display any and may be set to 1. We also pointed out in another note that both terms could display the same information, namely $-e_i/T$ or a constant times $-e_i/T$. We then formed entropy as: $\sum_i \{p_1(e_i) \text{ or } p_1(e_i)^q \text{ for the Shannon or Tsallis case}\} F(p_1(e_i))$. Here $p_1(e_i)$ is normalized.

In this note, we argue that the results of (1) may be obtained in such a manner, i.e $p(e_i) dF/dp(e_i) = \text{constant } e_i/T$. In this way one may find a Tsallis entropy with a power law probability directly. As a result, we do not start with an a priori power law probability, but derive it from the general $F(p)$ and $p dF/dp = \text{constant} * F(p)$ approach.

Procedure of (1)

The authors of (1) begin with a power law probability:

$$p(e_i) = C (e_i/T)^{-g} \quad ((1))$$

They calculate C explicitly and show it is independent of T (temperature). Their next goal is to find an expression for entropy so they may show that it is of a Tsallis form and then argue that ((1)), instead of $\exp q(e_i)$, is also a solution of the Tsallis problem. Thus, the key is find an expression for entropy, which they define as:

$$S = k \sum_i g(p(e_i)) \quad \text{such that } g(p(e_i)) = 0 \text{ if } p(e_i) = 1 \text{ or } 0 \quad ((2)) \quad \text{Here } p(e_i) \text{ is normalized.}$$

$$\text{Secondly, they write: } 0 = \sum_i \{e_i - kT dg/dp(e_i)\} dp(e_i) \quad \text{define} = \sum_i K_i dp(e_i) \quad ((3))$$

Thus: $dg/dp(e_i) = 1/(kT) \{e_i - K_i\}$ and one may find dg by integrating over dp .

The key idea is then to express e_i in terms of $p(e_i)$ which is done by using ((1)), i.e.

$$e_i/T = C_1 p(e_i)^{-1/g} \quad ((4))$$

Upon integrating one obtains the form:

$$g(p(e_i)) = C_2 \{- p(e_i) + p(e_i)^{1-1/g}\} \quad ((5))$$

When one sums over i , one obtains a Tsallis form with $q = 1 - 1/g = q$, but a power law ((1)) is the solution instead of $\exp(q e_i)$.

We try to obtain this same result based on a method we have used for Shannon, Tsallis and even Kaniadakis entropies.

F(p) = -e_i/T Approach

We suggest that Shannon and Tsallis entropies are linked with the existence of a function $F(p(e_i))$ such that:

$$F(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T \quad ((6)) \quad \text{Here } p(e_i) \text{ is unnormalized. In the Shannon case, } F = \ln.$$

Entropy is given by: $-\sum_i p(e_i) F(p(e_i))$ if $p(e_i)$ (when normalized) is the probability used to create averages of e_i power n . In the Shannon case it is, but in the Tsallis case one uses $p(e_i)$ power q , so:

$$\text{Tsallis case: Entropy} = -\sum_i p(e_i)^q F(p(e_i)) \quad ((7))$$

The problem is that ((6)) and ((7)) don't yield the solution of F . To obtain this, we argued in (2) that one should consider the first average: $\sum_i e_i p(e_i)$ (unnormalized) as representing the relevant e_i information in the problem. Thus:

$$d/dp(e_i) \{ p(e_i) F(p(e_i)) \} = F(p(e_i)) + p(e_i) dF/dp(e_i) \quad ((8)) \text{ in the Shannon case and}$$

$$d/dp(e_i) \{ p(e_i)^q F(p(e_i)) \} = F(p(e_i)) + p(e_i)^q dF/dp \quad ((9)) \text{ in the Tsallis case}$$

Setting the second term equal to the constant 1 allows one to explicitly solve for $F(p)$ as shown in (2). In the Tsallis case one requires that the solution $F(q, p(e_i)) = \ln(p)$ for $q=1$.

The Kaniadakis case is more subtle, but still follows from $F(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$ and $dF/dp(e_i) = 1/L F(p(e/a))$ where L and a are scaling constants.

As we have noted before, a second possible solution is to have the second term in ((8)), ((9)) represent the e_i/T information multiplied by a constant, instead of simply being 1. We suggest that such an approach leads ultimately to the $p_1(e_i) = C p(e_i)^{-g}$ of (1).

To start, we use $p(e_i)$ as the unnormalized probability which would average e_i as there is no a priori $p(e_i)^{-q}$ in the problem. Then:

$$F(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T \quad \text{and} \quad p(e_i) \frac{dF}{dp(e_i)} = C e_i/T \quad ((10))$$

$$\text{This leads to: } p \frac{dF}{dp} = -C F \quad \text{or} \quad F = - p(e_i)^{-C} \quad ((11))$$

If $C = 1/g$, then $p = (e_i/T)^{-g}$ is the inverse of F . which is the power law desired ((12))

Entropy is then: $\sum_i p(e_i) p(e_i)^{-1/g}$. One may add a constant to entropy to obtain:

$$\{1 - \sum_i p_1(e_i)^{(1-1/g)}\} \text{ constant } ((13)) \text{ which is essentially the Tsallis result of (1).}$$

In the final writing of entropy, we substitute unnormalized probabilities $p(e_i)$ with normalized ones $p_1(e_i)$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the authors of (1) start with an a priori power law $p(e_i) = C e_i^{-g}$ and argue that it leads to a Tsallis entropy. They obtain a general expression for entropy through an integration process which we describe in paragraph 1 (and is shown in (1)). The main idea of (1) is that a power law may be the solution of a Tsallis problem instead of the usual $\exp(q e_i)$. We note that (1) considers $p(e_i)$ as the probability which creates averages of moments of e_i^n . In the usual Tsallis case, it is $p(e_i)^{-q}$.

In previous notes (2), we have argued for a general approach using unnormalized probabilities, which is applicable to Shannon, Tsallis and Kaniadakis (with some modifications) approaches. The idea is to begin with a function F such that $F(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$. The next step is to mimic the first moment (or any moment) of $e_i p(e_i)$ for Shannon or $p(e_i)^{-q} e_i$ for Tsallis, i.e. $p(e_i) F(p(e_i))$ or $p(e_i)^{-q} F(p(e_i))$. We then take $d/dp(e_i)$ of this expression. The term $F(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$ represents all of the e_i information so we argue that the second term $p \frac{dF}{dp}$ or $p^{-q} \frac{dF}{dp} = 1$ and obtain either Shannon's or Tsallis cases. (For the Tsallis case, $q=1$ must yield $F(p, q=1) = \ln$).

Here, we suggest that a second solution is to use, instead of $p \frac{dF}{dp} = 1$ (p is the averaging probability used by (1)), $p \frac{dF}{dp} = \text{constant } (-e_i/T)$. From this we obtain the power law $p(e_i) = (e_i/T)^{-g}$ (unnormalized) and a Tsallis entropy as shown above. As a result, the procedure of considering d/dp acting on: {averaging probability} $\cdot F(p)$ leads to various forms of $F(p)$ and p solutions. We suggest that the power law result of (1) is one of these and obtain it

from this procedure instead of introducing it a priori. (Shannon, regular Tsallis with $\exp q$ and even Kaniadakis are linked with the approach, we argue.)

References

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